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Passing our students while we fail upwards: Reflections on the inaugural year of CSU Engineering

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ABSTRACT

CSU Engineering University introduced its radical new Civil Engineering degree in 2016. The program (described in full elsewhere) was deliberately designed to eschew the traditional lecture-lab-model of engineering education, and instead focus on training student engineers in an authentic and actual engineering work environment. The program was built upon a strong foundation of engineering educational research from around the globe, with clearly identified best practices being woven together to form the CSU Engineering curriculum. Each of the pieces was chosen for its proven impact in its original environment; with the challenge for CSU Engineering being how to make the integration of these pieces work without the underlying traditional environment. While the overall program rollout was a success, there were a number of mistakes made along the way; this paper highlights some of our key learnings, and the improvements made for the second year to overcome them.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: New Program Development, Academic Integrity, Program Culture

INTRODUCTION

CSU Engineering is a new program established in 2016. This program was established from scratch in a university that has not previously taught engineering. As such, there was a significant opportunity to build a revolutionary new program structure and philosophy [1]. With this opportunity, however, brings the risks of operating something new, and the inevitability of making mistakes. This paper will outline the key changes necessary for the second year of our program, based on the lessons learned from the inaugural year of operation.

To a certain extent the program has been immunised to its mistakes as a result of its culture and philosophy, and our clearly defined mission of living our spoken values. We have a clearly defined goal of educating entrepreneurial engineers; as such it is essential that we ourselves demonstrate an entrepreneurial mind-set and outlook. All of our students are aware that ours is a new course, and that it is in the first years of its operation. As a result they are more understanding that the program is yet to settle down into steady-state operation.

A key objective of the program is to train entrepreneurial engineers; in order to be authentic in this space the program itself, and the academics, need to be (and need to be seen to be) entrepreneurial. Entrepreneurship requires the taking of risks, and a willingness to make mistakes along the way. An important part of entrepreneurship is the ability to "fail upwards" - to make mistakes, learn from them, and improve practice. In this way some of our mistakes were forgivable as providing an authentic teaching environment; although care had to be taken not to rely upon this as an excuse. In this culture, our mistakes are not to be hidden – they are to be presented to the students as teachable moments, and as examples of what it is to be an entrepreneurial engineer.

1 TOPIC ACQUISITION

Students at CSU Engineering complete a sequence of three semester-long PBL-style challenges across the first three semesters; after this point they then commence work placements in industry. The underlying technical curriculum that supports the projects is broken down into fine-grained topics, where each topic is intended to take around three hours to complete. These topics are then arranged into a tree structure where the recommended learning order is made explicit (fig 1).

In this way the students engage with theory at the point at which it is required in their work, rather than in a synchronous syllabus driven manner. This has the advantage of ensuring the content is relevant at the point at which it is learned; it introduces the risk of how the student manage their progression through the tree.

Students are required to complete a total of at least 240 topics from the tree before they are eligible to go on industry placement in their fourth semester. 80 of these topics are compulsory, selected after a process of engaging with our industry partners [2] the students are free to choose the other 160 from throughout the tree.

Fig 1: The Topic tree

A deliberate choice was made to prioritise independent learning over micromanagement. Intermediate deadlines could have been included throughout the subject, whether on a semester-by-semester or even week-by-week basis. The philosophical challenge with this is that it encourages a shallow, compliance-based engagement with the curriculum – topics are completed when a deadline looms, rather than topics being completed when that knowledge is valuable for the on-going challenges. It was also important that we be able to certify to employers that our cadets are self-directed independent learners, rather than students who are able to deliver when micromanaged to deadlines.

The emergent problem was that giving student engineers the freedom to manage their own workload also gives them the freedom to dig themselves a hole they can't get out of, and this was a risk that we did not mitigate well enough.

There were essentially no consequences for an inadequate rate of progression through the topic tree. The challenges had mid- and end-of-semester milestones that needed to be met, including public presentations and exhibitions at which a lack of achievement would have been clearly highlighted. The topic tree, however, has only two requirements, and neither of them manifest until the very end of the three-semester subject.

The cohort effectively bifurcated on the basis of their ability to learning independently. Student engineers with good internal management skills planned well, and worked

consistently throughout the three semesters. Student engineers who lacked the self-directed learning skills consistently put off the work – utilising the flexibility not as to when they did the work, but rather as to if they did the work.

This led to two sub-cohorts – one who was up to date, and on track to successfully complete the subject, and one that was well behind, and unlikely to complete. The structure of the program, however, meant that there were no explicit differences in the way that these two groups were treated. This was perceived as an injustice on the part of the up to date students, who felt that they were entitled to better treatment on the grounds that they had worked harder.

In order to prevent this from occurring with our second cohort, it was essential to give the students a regular signal as to what progress was expected from them. A public “scoreboard” with all students’ progress displayed was considered as an option. This would introduce clear accountability; however it would also have consequences for students’ privacy. There was also a concern that while it would potentially introduce a motivating level of competition amongst those who were performing well, it was likely to serve as a demotivator to the students who were performing the least well – the ones most in need of support.

As such a neutral cadence for progress was required. This is provided through the introduction of a “MetroGnome” (Fig 2). Each week the teaching team announce to the students the fictional progress of the MetroGnome; this allows us to set a benchmark level of minimum performance, and to trigger conversations with students who are falling behind. The MetroGnome’s performance is calibrated to be somewhat below average initially, but nonetheless still adequate to eventually be successful throughout the course. While we are concerned that students have taken this signal to represent adequate progress rather than a minimum, evidence on student progress shows that the second cohort is progressing far quicker overall than the first cohort.

Fig 2: The MetroGnome

Another area where we did not provide sufficient up front consequence was in the balance of contributions to group projects. Teams were accountable to their mentors on a weekly basis; however it was not always clear from these meetings how teams were managing their workloads. It became apparent that some kind of moderation was necessary; however by the time this could be implemented it was a post-hoc reconstruction, rather than a week-by-week capturing of actual inputs. The net result

of this process did indeed mitigate some of the more egregious imbalances; but there was little perceived direct consequence for those who were only mildly underperforming.

To address this issue, we introduced the SparkPLUS teamwork tool [3,4] commencing in the start of the second year. SparkPLUS has the ability to capture on a week by week basis each team member's perceptions of their own contributions, as well as those of their colleagues. In this way unbalanced teams can be detected; further, imbalances in perceptions of contribution can also be identified. Conflict in teams can arise from mismatches in effort; but there is also a significant risk of conflict if a student's self-perception of their contribution differs from the way their colleagues value their input.

Throughout the first semester of use, the SparkPLUS results have not been automatically released to students each week. Mentors who have chosen to discuss the results each week have been able to promote better working relationships within teams; however teams whose mentors who have not emphasised this data still display some unbalanced behaviours. The decision not to automate the release was taken on the grounds of privacy and unfamiliarity with the software; it is likely that for the second and subsequent semesters of use the information will be passed on each week.

2 ACADEMIC MISCONDUCT

CSU Engineering operates a very pro-active culture of Integrity, drawing from the safety culture to publicly count the number of days without an incident. There has been only one identified academic incident in the first three semesters of operation of the program. The origins of the incident were traced to workload-related panic, rather than a deliberate intent to deceive; nonetheless the cheating occurred and our counter had to be reset.

We did not think through all the way the consequences of sending a very loud public signal that one of the cohort had cheated. Normally incidents of academic misconduct are not publicised; they remain fully anonymous, and invisible to the rest of the cohort. We did not identify the student in question; nonetheless rumours spread throughout the student body.

In particular this served to further divide our bifurcated cohort – the stronger students were clear that it had not been one of them that had been responsible, and this increased the existing tension between the two sub-cohorts.

The tension – and its implicit lack of trust / faith – manifested again when we discussed adjusting the controls we had used to address the academic misconduct issue. We made changes in our IT systems to prevent a recurrence of the incident; however a side effect of this change was that some legitimate access to the system was made more difficult. When we discussed with the cohort whether they wished us to remove this control, and to make the learning process easier, the feedback we received was a clear no. The Student engineers preferred that we did not re-introduce the risk of misconduct, even at the price of reduced functionality – a sign that they did not trust their weaker colleagues.

3 MANAGING CADET PLACEMENTS

Our first cohort of cadet placements saw 17 Cadet Engineers placed with industry partners. These placements are full-time work positions, with the cadets paid by the employers while they are with their organisations. This placement program is one of the key points of distinction for the program, running contrary to the current trend in

Australia to move away from industry experience for undergraduate engineers. The success of this placement program is critical to CSU Engineering overall; while it has worked well in the first instance, there is still room for improvement.

The process for allocating cadets to partners was entirely utilitarian in nature. A parameterised “Happiness Function” was developed to give comparable numerical values to alternative allocations; and then a decision tree was built to generate those alternative allocation patterns. Some matchings were common to all patterns – situations where a cadet is a host’s first choice and vice versa – but other matchings offered degrees of freedom to optimise a solution.

This process was not finalised until the actual “Mad Monday” on which the matchings took place; as such it was not made clear to the cadets and the hosts in advance. While there was a clear understanding that preferences would be considered, and (we thought) a clear understanding that not everyone can get their first preference, the exact mechanisms were not clear to all involved. This led to some irate conversations on the Tuesday when the matchings were announced.

In our attempts not to burden industry partners with training too early, we left out delivering important information until too late. We wanted confirmation that they were in fact going to have a cadet placed with them, so that we we’re training Host Engineers at organisations that were orphaned; instead we ended up withholding information from the larger majority of Host Engineers that did receive a cadet. Key amongst that information was the process by which we place our cadets; and so the process itself was explained many times rather than just the once.

4 CONCLUSION

Balancing the need for providing a safe space to fail upwards with the need to train engineers who can be compliant with standards and specifications was a difficult challenge for the team in the first instance, particularly during the single instance of academic misconduct that arose during the year. Mimicking the safety culture has provided an accessible way for the student engineering cohort to adopt an appropriate attitude towards academic integrity.

Difficulties also arose with the extent of scaffolding necessary to develop independent learning skills in the students. Too much support undermines the goal of instilling independence; too little support leaves the students lost. The first year of the program leaned too far towards freedom rather than close monitoring; an alternative approach employing gamification rather than coercion has been implemented for our second year. Early indications are positive; however it is too early to tell if the MetroGnome will provide a sufficient level of guidance to avoid the introduction of more coercive, enforceable intermediate milestones in the future.

CSU Engineering has been able to live the value of failing upwards – our program is a safe space for reflective practitioners to make mistakes, and to improve their practices for the next iteration. The second year of our implementation is already an improvement upon the first; these measures are improving learning outcomes for our students, both directly and in the culture they support.

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